

The Role of Power and Patriarchy in Gender Based Harassment: A Structural Analysis

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Abstract

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Gender based harassment is not just a single person problem rather it is deeply rooted social problem that arise from a long history of inequality. In the present system of society man have more power, controlling all the institutions and making rules of society in which women are often being ignored. This system makes easier for men to misuse power and harass women. This paper described that women are harassed through different ways such as physical, psychological, verbal and workplace harassment, it shows that how this behavior of man is considered normal. A historical view shows that this system of patriarchy starts thousands of years ago and it became stronger through the laws, religion, colonial system and economic changes. Even today man still holds almost all the leadership positions in politics and in the economic system while, women are still facing harassment, low wages, and inequality. With the passage of time women gain many rights but still today women

are facing discrimination in many places. This paper based on the qualitative type of research that focus on the patriarchal structure of society.

Key words: Patriarchy, Men, Women, Harassment, Power.

Introduction

In most societies, patriarchy encourages the opinion that men should have more authority, voice, and control, while women should be quiet, obedient, and less powerful. The concept of patriarchy used mostly in feminist theories, where men are considered powerful (Hadi, 2017). It shapes how people grow up and conduct themselves, and often this happens very unconsciously. Because men are perceived to be natural-born leaders or decision-makers, they dominate the workplace, public space, and even family environment. In the workplace, men generally occupy higher positions and might misuse their authority by making inappropriate comments, demands, or threats. All these types of activities threaten the women that they will lose their jobs. On the other hand, men consider it their right to harass women and society expecting that women should ignore it and should focus on their work. In many families especially in rural areas patriarchal

system exist and man is considered the head of the society so, it is man to decide about the education, work or personal life of women. As time passes these inequalities in a society are consider to be normal or as a part of life. This harassment is not about just one person or individual but many women are facing this harassment silently.

If we look at the social structure of a society, we will notice that there is unequal power between the men and women. The societies with patriarchal structure have man with more power or always superior and women always considered as subordinate or lower than men. This structure of society tells us clearly that who is the leader or whose decisions are implemented in a society. At many places women get harass from men that are working at higher positions, at this position men often misuse their power. Supervisors often use their power and ask women for sexual favors; it creates insecurity among women. The fear of losing job, damage of reputation and many other things like this keeps many victims silent. Many women didn't even tell anything to their families or relatives think that society will label them as a bad guy.

Many organizations and institutions have week reporting system or in other hand the system is male dominated or patriarchal. Instead of support the victims such type of institutions focuses mainly on the male reputation and ignore the issues of women. Policies are present just on the paper there in no implementation in daily life. This structure of society further encourages men to exploit women as there are no check and balance in a society (Dr. Amber Ferdoos, 2016).

At the level of society, patriarchy change the beliefs of peoples about the gender that how men and women should behave. It tells men that being dominant or powerful is a normal thing being a man while on the other hand women are expected to be silent and quiet. These expectations exist in the people's mind from a long-term era now, without realizing man consider it as a normal part of life. If any women try to eliminate this barrier of inequality or try to challenge the patriarchal system harassment is used to push her back and also punish that women for crossing the limits. If a women get harassed society often ask questions to women no one talks about the harasser. This also create instability where a women face all the hurdle's and there no one to ask any question from the harasser. Women feel alone because there is no one to support her and system also work in favor of harasser.

How women are harassed

Social system wherein men have more authority, control most of the resources, and make major decisions. The imbalance gives men greater social, economic, and physical power, which can be misused to harass, silence, or intimidate women. Due to such deeply ingrained structures in society, harassment gets normalized, ignored, or even justified. The main ingredient of harassment is power. Men in better positions bosses, teachers, employers, community leaders, or older males within the family customarily abuse that position in attempts to control women. This includes the threat of losing a job, reputation, or safety. If a man believes he has the right to dominate or control, harassment becomes the avenue to prove one's superiority. A lot of women remain silent out of fear that they might lose their jobs, damage their social image, or face further harm. Harassment is a major problem at workplaces, but after the me-too movement awareness increase between the people (Frida Pilgaard, 2023).

Through the patriarchal system of society everyone believed that men are dominant and have more power so, it is to be considered that man can control everything even can harass women.

Cultural structure also shows that if man is aggressive or talking in a loud voice with females than it is normal and at the same time women are expected to be polite and tolerant. Power and patriarchy design the overall structure of society.

Different ways of harassment

Verbal harassment is a way of harassment in which women are threatened through sexual jokes or passing comments on their appearance. It also includes whistling or making kissing sounds. This behavior can have severe psychological effects on women. This type of harassment occurs mostly in the public places and the work places. Physical harassment means the touching of someone without taking her permission or without informing her. There are different types of physical harassment. It may include unwanted touching, blocking someone's way, physical attachment like hugs, forcing for sex and threatening gestures. This kind of harassment causes physical illness, mental stress, fear and lack of safety among the women. It shows men's power over women's bodies. Mostly women are the victims of sexual harassment (Hadi, 2017).

Psychological or emotional harassment affects a woman's mental health. It is an abstract or invisible type of harassment but has alarming impacts. It has many forms like fear of harm and violence, continuously facing criticism, blackmailing and isolation from the friends and family. This type of harassment causes stress, anxiety, depression and mental illness. Workplace harassment happens when colleagues, employers and boss create such type of environment that is unsafe for a woman. They use their resources in an un appropriate manner to harass women's. Types of this harassment include sending unethical messages or emails, threatening them to fire for not listening to their inappropriate demands, insisting them to fulfill their sexual demands in place of their promotions and gender discrimination. It causes stress, loss of confidence and even forces them to quit their jobs and further avoid to think about their career opportunities.

Historical Context of Patriarchy

Patriarchy is a system where men hold most of the power. This system of patriarchy began around 5,000 to 6,000 (Lerner, 1986) years ago. This was the time when people moved from hunting and gathering to farming and owning land. In this early time period men and women were considered equal because they shared work and resources. But once farming started everything changed. When societies began to grow crops, animals, and extra food for peoples, men controlled all this property and all this gave man more power than women. Slowly all this turned into a system where man held the authority and made all the rule.

Ancient societies also formulated laws to support male power. As an instance, the Code of Hammurabi from Mesopotamia, treated females like inheritance that could be transfer from parents to offspring. Women's bodies, sexuality, and ability to have children became things that men tried to control. In ancient Greek and Roman societies, women were also given a lower status by law. They needed a male guardian all their lives, and they could not vote, own property freely, or participate in politics. They were legally seen as dependents, not full citizens. Over time, these early practices laid the groundwork for patriarchal systems that continued for thousands of years. In many societies this tradition still exists as it was in ancient times. In many developing countries especially in backward areas men still thought women as their property, and women are not allowed to speak in any matter of their lives (Lerner, 1986)

Religious and Philosophical Legitimization

Many major religions and philosophical ideas helped strengthen and justify patriarchy. They did this by presenting male authority as something approved by God, nature, or moral law. Because of this, unequal gender roles became seen as normal, natural, or even holy. In Judeo-Christian traditions, some interpretations of the story of creation say that woman was made from man and blame her for the first sin. These ideas were often used to say that women should be obedient to men and that men were naturally the leaders (Attoh, 2017)

In Islamic law, women were given important rights such as the right to own property and receive inheritance but the legal system also established male guardianship. It shows that men were thought to be the leaders of women and then they by using this authority, they distribute inheritance unequally and owned more authority in family issues. Even the philosophers in that time supported patriarchy. For example: the most influential philosopher of Greek stated that women are weak than men and are created for just giving births. Later the societies used this way of thinking about women's role in society. The Confucian philosophy in East Asia gave three basic points about the women obedience. According to him, they should listen to their father when they are unmarried, to their husbands after marriage and to their sons in their old age. This philosophy made the women dependent on men in their whole lives.

Together, these religious teachings and philosophical beliefs gave strong justification for keeping women out of education, leadership, and public life for centuries. AS Islam or other religions also gives men more power than women so man also tried to show their superiority in every aspect of their lives.

Feudalism and Colonial Expansion

During medieval times in Europe, patriarchy became even stronger. Feudal laws gave most power and property to the oldest son (primogeniture), and married women lost their legal identity under a system called coverture. This meant that once a woman got married, she was legally considered part of her husband. She could not own property, make contracts, or even keep her children if the marriage ended. Between the 15th and 17th (Hanks, 2021) centuries, Europe saw the thousands of women especially healers, midwives, or women who challenged male authority were suspected of magic. Around 40,000 to 100,000 (Kgalta; Kgalta, 2012) people were killed, and most of them were women.

This was a form of extreme patriarchal violence meant to control and silence women. When European powers colonized Asia, Africa, and the Americas, they spread their patriarchal systems around the world. In many places, indigenous societies had more balanced or flexible gender roles. But colonial rulers replaced these systems with European laws that took away women's traditional rights such as land ownership, leadership roles, or economic independence. Colonized women suffered both racism and patriarchy, creating a double burden. They faced discrimination for being women and for being part of colonized groups, leading to harsh and unequal living conditions. In this system women were tired and want to gain equal rights as of men. Man, also remain dominant and suppress all the rights of women's.

Industrial Capitalism and the Doctrine of Separate Spheres

During the Industrial Revolution in the 18th and 19th (Eliska Vioni, 2023) centuries, gender roles became even more divided. A new idea called separate spheres became popular. According to this belief, men belonged in the public world working in factories, doing business, and taking part in politics while women were expected to stay at home, take care of the family, and run the household. This thinking made women's domestic work seem like a natural duty or an act of love, instead of real, valuable labor. Because of this, women were not paid for their work at home and became financially dependent on men's wages. It taught that a good woman should be pure, religious, submissive, and focused on home life.

These ideals limited women's freedom and prevented them from participating fully in public life. Even early labor unions and socialist movements though they fought for workers' rights were often led by men who did not support gender equality. Many unions tried to keep women out of factories and argued for a family wage, meaning men should earn enough to support wives who stayed at home. This idea kept women in secondary, dependent positions. Legally, women also faced major restrictions. In Britain, married women could not own property in their own name until the Married Women's Property Acts (1870–1882).

And women's right to vote came only after long, difficult suffrage movements that lasted well into the 20th century. Men take advantage from females in every field of life. Women perform work in factories and all other institutes but their wages were low as compared to mans. In many places women were considered the subordinates of mans.

20th Century: Formal Rights and Persistent Structures

In the 20th century, many countries finally introduced laws that gave women basic rights. Women won the right to vote, gained access to education, could own property, and were protected by new employment laws. On paper, it looked like equality had been achieved. But legal equality did not end deeper, structural inequalities. Sociologist R.W. Connell explains this through the idea of the patriarchal dividend. This means that men as a group continue to benefit from old gender systems often without even realizing it because society was built around male advantage for so long (Dr. Amber Ferdoos, 2016)

After World War II, patriarchy simply changed shape. Women entered the workforce in record numbers, but they were mostly pushed into lower-paid jobs considered women's work, such as teaching, nursing, and clerical roles. Meanwhile, most women still had to manage the second shift doing the majority of cooking, cleaning, and childcare at home after finishing their paid job. In the late 1970s and 1980s, the sexual harassment was recognized as a big problem for women in the society. The weird behaviors of many people were taken as normal or was being ignored before that time. Catharine MacKinnon, the feminist scholar stated that these behaviors were actually ways men used power to control or intimidate women, that showed how patriarchy continued to operate in the daily life. It was shown that women are being given the rights that are equal to men but that was not right, even then women were not given many rights.

Contemporary Manifestations and Global Variations

In today's time, patriarchy still exists, but it has more complex and different types. works in more subtle and hidden ways. In place of open discrimination, now the societies have retained

biases, cultures at workplace, and other things that gives men more power than women. If we see the glass ceiling concept it also stops women to reach at higher positions in every field (Hanks, 2021). Many movements push back women to make progress in life such as the backlash movement group. Such type of actions show that men always try to protect themselves when they feel any threat.

In the global economy, the concept of neoliberal capitalism also created many types of inequality. Wages of women are low than men in every field. Women are working as a worker in factories and industries. All this shows that the exploitation or harassment of women still exist but their pattern is change now. In different countries of world patriarchy exist in different forms. We cannot end this concept of patriarchy. In many countries patriarchy is clear in laws and customs such as laws of male leadership such as laws in Saudi Arabia here women are restricted and are facing many barriers. In many countries patriarchy is working as a hidden concept such as lower representation of women in politics and other institutions (Attoh, 2017).

Report and global research from the World Economic Forum 2023 explains that most of the societies in world underrepresenting the women in all areas or fields such as economics, politics and cultural. If we look at the system, we will notice that modern gender-based harassment is linked with the structure of the old time that was exist thousands of years ago. Solving gender-based harassment is not easy it requires to change the whole structure of society.

A Structural Analysis

Overview of structural theory

Structural theory is a concept that tells us about the problems and inequalities in a society by looking at the whole system or structure of the society. It focuses on the system of society, not focus on persons or individuals.

Power and Patriarchy in Political Structure

Power and the role of man in society design and run the political structure. It also tells us that how system will work and who will gain the maximum power in this system. In this system of government men also has given more power and control. From the executive bodies to the legislative position all the major position are under the man. Even in the current time democracy all the decision-making positions are under the man control. The rules and behavior of this political system is also made for the favor of man. All this political system shows that men and women are different, so this political system shows that men are powerful from the ancient times. This system always supports male ways of thinking and working.

In old times women were not allowed to caste votes or buy property which create inequality among the societies. Even today when women gain most of their rights but still, they are deprived from their rights such as they cannot participate in the political decisions and also, they don't have enough money for political campaigns. The division of political labors also give women duties related to health, education and political awareness among peoples and it gave mans serious role related foreign policy, defense and finance. In our system it is to be considered that women are only for household chores or for the protection of children while men are considered to participate in politics or public life. After the emergence of feminists' theory and feminists' movements women representation increased in politics. By just increasing the number

of women in political structure we can not say that now, women will enjoy equal rights as of man but there is a need to change all the rules of political structure so women can get equal power as of man.

Power and Patriarchy in economic structure

The economy of any country is greatly affected by the power and patriarchy. Patriarchy gives man more control over resources and money. It gives man more importance and undervalue women work. Women were not allowed to get property and financially independent from ancient times therefore women still not allowed to take loans and business opportunities. These are not paid equally as of men even the work is same. Their wages are low in all workplaces. These are performing their duties at home all the day but there is no pay for that work (Johnston, 2025) This free labor of women is playing an important role in boosting the economy of any country or in the GDP of any state.

Most of the companies, bank and economic decisions are under the men control this shows that economic structure just talks about the male benefits and ignores women rights. This shows that women in the developing countries especially single mothers, older women face money problems as not gaining enough money to live a peaceful life. To improve this system, we should end this wages discrimination among genders.

Power and patriarchy in cultural structure

Culture is shaped by patriarchy; it makes men's power appear normal. Society teaches men to be leaders and women followers through language, religion, media, and education. The cultural rules define masculinity as strong and superior, while femininity is seen as weak or secondary. The social media and the traditions or cultures also support the patriarchy system as they show women as child's caretakers, things to represent beauty and their romance partners. Although the online spaces allow feminist voices to resist, they again are the part in the spreading of harassment (Eliska Vioni, 2023). Violence justification against women creates the center of patriarchal culture, with devastating beliefs such as victim-blaming and honor codes. The women bodies are controlled by the challenges like child marriage, FGM, and dowry violence. In addition to this, patriarchy makes links with caste, community, and colonial history, producing different challenges for women of different societies.

Conclusion

This paper explains that gender-based harassment is not just due to any single person but is the result of vast history and culture of patriarchy and unequal distribution of power in society. From the past times times to the digital world, men have gained great power and authority at living places, workplaces, religion, politics, and the economy. This gender inequality gives a huge leverage to men for controlling resources, take on decisions, and use their powers in inappropriate way. On the other hand, the expect the silence from women side at this unequal treatment. All these types of harassment-verbal, physical, emotional, and workplace, still exist now because society has not stopped taking male dominance normal and highlighting women's suffering. Although in the current days, women hold many legal rights in the 20th century, it is still very away from real equality. Women still face low wages, discrimination, limited seats in

politics, unsafe workplaces, and social pressure to remain silent. In conclusion, harassment cannot be completely ended by giving punishments to individuals alone, but by altering the systems and structures that have kept patriarchy on its way. Society should reshape political institutions, economic structure, workplace traditions, and societal belief systems in such systems that give women equality in power and safety. By doing this, there will be less gender-based harassment and a more equitable community if we change the structure, not only the behavior of any person.

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